

Exploiting highly heterogeneous systems with stencil applications

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Abstract. While CPUs, GPUs, and FPGAs present particular advantages for different classes of High Performance Computing Applications, Iterative Stencil Loop (ISL) is a class of parallel applications with efficient implementations for all of them. Thus, this class is an interesting case of use to test the potential of using simultaneously different classes of heterogeneous devices.

EPSILOG is a parallel skeleton framework designed to easily program and deploy ISL applications on heterogeneous platforms. It provides a programming abstraction and a transparent coordination system to work with different types of devices.

In this work, we improve EPSILOG and its performance portability layer to support key features for developing and operating optimized kernels on FPGAs. The new EPSILOG version allows the execution of efficient stencil programs simultaneously on CPUs, GPUs, and FPGA accelerators. We discuss how to test the computing power of each different device and use this information in an EPSILOG data-partition policy to obtain a balanced load distribution across them. We present an experimental study using a classical heat-transfer stencil example in a highly heterogeneous system to show the efficiency of EPSILOG programs when using a CPU, a GPU, and an FPGA simultaneously.

Keywords: Heterogeneous Computing · FPGAs · Parallel skeletons · Stencil

1 Introduction

Iterative Stencil Loops (ISL) is an important application class in High Performance Computing (HPC). They are used in many fields such as image processing [2], solving partial differential equations [13], or physical simulations [16], among others. In stencil computations, cells in a multidimensional grid are iteratively updated based on the previous values of neighboring cells. The neighborhood is determined using a specific pattern, also known as the *stencil*. Since many applications require computing stencil operations over massive amounts

of data (millions or billions of elements), the acceleration of stencil kernels poses an interesting problem to the HPC community. In this context, heterogeneous supercomputers leveraging accelerators (GPUs, FPGAs, and ASICs) are often used to accelerate stencil computations.

FPGAs are used due to their acceleration capabilities and their flexibility to adapt to many different tasks. FPGAs have proven to be well-suited for accelerating stencil computations, achieving high performance and energy efficiency [5,20]. However, efficient FPGA programming entails significantly higher development efforts than other commodity accelerators, which often hinders their adoption for HPC tasks. High-Level Synthesis (HLS) tools or highly abstract programming languages, such as OpenCL or SYCL, ease these efforts, partially bridging the gap between FPGAs and other computation devices.

Additionally, heterogeneous computing approaches and techniques, where multiple different devices are leveraged concurrently for a single task, are needed to efficiently exploit highly heterogeneous systems, as well as to increase the memory capacity supported by the applications. Nevertheless, programming stencil applications for heterogeneous systems entails significant challenges, as devices of varying nature must be properly managed and coordinated by the host, using heterogeneous data partitions to balance the load, and communicating data across memory spaces managed with different low-level technologies.

In this work, we expand EPSILOD, a C/C++ high-productivity parallel programming skeleton for Iterative Stencil Loop computations on distributed heterogeneous systems [4], to leverage FPGA devices alongside other kinds of accelerator devices. This enhances the parallel skeleton’s portability to exploit CPUs, GPUs, and FPGAs concurrently in a single program execution.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We extend EPSILOD, a high-productivity parallel programming skeleton for ISL computation on distributed heterogeneous systems, to support FPGA devices. We discuss the particular challenges and limitations of adding FPGA support in cooperative heterogeneous frameworks and a solution to integrate FPGA-optimized kernels that cooperate with other devices efficiently.
- We discuss a simple method to identify the data-partition parameters to generate a balanced distribution of load across heterogeneous devices.
- We present an experimental study to show the efficiency of our approach, using a classical heat-transfer stencil and a hybrid platform with one instance of each type of device. The study includes performance comparisons between generic device-agnostic kernels and FPGA-optimized kernels, and between scenarios with single and multiple concurrent devices: CPU, GPU, and FPGA.

All the code developed to carry out this work is publicly available at https://gitlab.com/trasgo-group-valladolid/controllers/-/tree/25_HP_epsilonFPGA.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses related work. Section 3 describes EPSILOD and its building blocks. Section 4 provides insight into the integration of FPGA support into EPSILOD. Section 5

describes the experimental study. Finally, Section 6 provides the conclusion of this work and discusses future work.

2 Related work

Stencil computations are a fundamental building block in numerous scientific applications. Several programming tools and frameworks are proposed to facilitate their implementation and deployment. Given their iterative nature and memory-bound characteristics, optimizing stencil computations for different types of devices and accelerators is an important research area.

There is extensive literature for optimizing stencil computations on GPUs, reducing memory accesses, and improving throughput and energy efficiency (for example [14]). There are frameworks to automate stencil computation optimizations from higher-level abstractions for NVIDIA GPUs [9], using different backends for different GPU architectures (such as CUDA, AMD, or Intel) [15], or directly generating code for a portability layer, such as the SYCL heterogeneous programming model [8]. Several studies compare the performance portability of different approaches to different types of GPUs [1]. Some of them highlight that more abstract models, which provide a higher functional portability level, still may need additional tuning to achieve reasonable performance. This is especially significant when leveraging systems comprising FPGAs, as their performance portability with device-agnostic or GPU-optimized codes has been noted to be rather low [3]. Some implementations of modern portability layers, such as SYCL, allow the use of different backends for different device types; but using these backends at the same time to coordinate parts of the same application presents problems. For example, current implementations of SYCL fail to do automatic data transfers across any combination of backends.

Optimizations of stencil computations on FPGAs have also been extensively studied [5, 17, 20]. Frameworks to generate optimized stencil FPGA codes from abstract specifications or Domain-specific languages are proposed [11, 18], or even leveraging portability layers such as SYCL [10]. Some works that present an in-depth analysis of stencil computations on FPGAs show the effectiveness of low-level architecture-specific tuning for FPGAs. However, they also highlight the challenge of portability and generalization when targeting heterogeneous or multi-accelerator environments [12].

Some works propose general programming cross-platform frameworks capable of exploiting CPU, GPU, and FPGAs simultaneously. They address general workload balancing across different devices using dynamic scheduling of medium-grain tasks [6]. These frameworks do not exploit coarse-grain data partitions for data locality and other specific features of stencil computations.

Traditionally, research in heterogeneous computing systems has focused on platforms that combine a host CPU with a single accelerator. Many studies have explored the potential of CPU+GPU platforms, while others have concentrated on CPU+FPGA configurations. Although these works often arrive at similar conclusions regarding the requirements of stencil algorithms, such as spatial

and temporal data reuse patterns, they ultimately demand hardware-specific adaptations tailored to the underlying accelerator.

EPSILOG [4] uses a different approach. It is a parallel skeleton that implements a coordination mechanism optimized for executing stencil applications, using coarse-grain partitioning and communication across multiple heterogeneous devices. It uses a portability layer to integrate multiple kernel implementations, which can be generic or optimized and tuned for specific devices.

3 EPSILOG: A parallel skeleton for stencil applications

This section describes EPSILOG, the parallel skeleton whose capabilities are expanded in this work, as well as its building blocks.

3.1 EPSILOG overview

EPSILOG is a parallel skeleton for generic iterative stencil computations in distributed heterogeneous systems. It can distribute the execution of stencil computations across devices of different computation capabilities, with policies to balance the workload, and coordinate the execution and communication across different device technologies, such as CPUs and GPUs of different vendors [4].

EPSILOG is presented as a reentrant, higher-order function written in C11, compatible with any modern C/C++ compiler. The function solves a fixed number of iterations of a geometric stencil computation, applying the stencil operator to each element of an n-dimensional array. The programmer provides the stencil operator as skeleton parameters, expressed as a *Stencil Description*. Listing 1.1 shows the Stencil Description for a classic 2D 4-point stencil.

Listing 1.1. Description of the 2D 4-point stencil to compute Poisson’s equation with a Jacobi method in EPSILOG. It defines the radius of the stencil, a pattern expressing the weight to apply to each neighbour, and the divisor factor.

```
HitShape shp_jacobi2d4 = hitShape((-1, 1), (-1, 1));
float patt_jacobi2d4[] = {
    0, 1, 0,
    1, 0, 1,
    0, 1, 0 };
float factor_jacobi2d4 = 4;
```

EPSILOG provides a tool to generate, from the Stencil Description, a *naïve* generic kernel implementation that works on any kind of device. Listing 1.2 provides the *naïve* kernel generated by the tool for the stencil described in listing 1.1. It is implemented using the API of the Controller programming model (discussed in Sect. 3.3), which is the portability layer used by EPSILOG. The user can provide several other custom kernel implementations for the same stencil with any desired optimization, including device- and vendor-specific ones. The best suitable kernel implementation is chosen at runtime for each device used.

Listing 1.2. Generic implementation for the 2D 4-point stencil in EPSILOG.

```

CTRL_KERNEL(updateCell_4, GENERIC, DEFAULT,
    KHitTile_float matrix, const KHitTile_float matrixCopy,
    const Epsilod_ext ext_params, {
    hit(matrix, thr_i, thr_j) = (hit(matrixCopy, thr_i - 1, thr_j) +
                                hit(matrixCopy, thr_i + 1, thr_j) +
                                hit(matrixCopy, thr_i, thr_j - 1) +
                                hit(matrixCopy, thr_i, thr_j + 1)) / 4;
});

```

3.2 EPSILOG workflow

Internally, EPSILOG performs the following operations:

1. **Distribution of the global data structures.** EPSILOG uses MPI for distributed computing, assigning one process to each device. It distributes the index space with a partition policy chosen among several options.
2. **Subdivision of the local arrays.** EPSILOG logically differentiates three parts on the local data structure for computation:
 - (a) *Halos*, added automatically by EPSILOG, to manage elements that are read, but not written, and might be received from other processes,
 - (b) *Borders*, which comprise elements that are updated and might be sent to other processes' halos, and
 - (c) *Inner*, including the elements that are only accessed by the local process.
3. **Generation of the communication pattern.** EPSILOG analyzes the Stencil Description and determines the data that should be communicated from the borders of one process to the halos of another process.
4. **Intra- and inter-process communications.** EPSILOG automatically performs the device-to-host and host-to-device data transfers, as well as the communications between processes.
5. **Overlapping of computation and communication.** EPSILOG first executes the proper stencil kernel to compute the border elements that must be communicated. The intra- and inter-process communications can begin immediately, and be overlapped with the computation of the Inner part.

3.3 The Controller model

The Controller model [19] is the portability layer upon which EPSILOG is built. It is a heterogeneous programming model implemented as a library that enables performance portability across CPU cores (using OpenMP), GPUs (using CUDA, HIP, or OpenCL), and Intel FPGAs (using Intel FPGA SDK for OpenCL). Controller integrates these vendor-specific technologies through different backends, coordinated by the same runtime layer. It presents a unified interface to the user and abstracts low-level device management and synchronization details.

A Controller object is associated with a particular instance of a computation device. The object manages the memory allocation, coordination, and communication of the host code with the device, and ensures the correct order of kernel

launches, based on the dependencies between the computations launched on different Controller objects. It also selects the best kernel implementation for the device assigned to it. The kernel codes are compiled using the vendor or native compiler for each device technology. The *naïve* generic kernels are compiled several times, one for each device technology.

Internally, the Controller model uses the Hitmap library [7] to carry out the data portability between device and host spaces. It uses a *HitTile* object to represent a data structure for computation. A HitTile is a kind of *fat-pointer* for multidimensional arrays, storing useful information such as its dimensions, index space, and partition information. It provides a common data layout and accessor functions for any kind of device. Hitmap also provides the functionalities to distribute and communicate data in *HitTile* objects across distributed processes.

The main features of Controller that make it suitable for this work are: (1) It supports data partitioning and distribution across distributed systems; (2) A simplified way to manage generic and manually optimized kernels for different technologies; (3) Its runtime supports coordination and data communications across different technologies, such as OpenMP, CUDA, HIP, or OpenCL, allowing the usage of all the different supported devices in the same execution.

4 Integrating FPGAs into EPSILOG

In this section, we discuss problems and solutions to integrate FPGAs in EPSILOG. EPSILOG applications may need to work with several different stencils. The previous Controller’s backend for FPGAs only supports one kernel definition per application due to the static compilation and linking process implemented. The backend is extended to search and load at runtime the kernels’ binaries from an arbitrary path in the file system. Additionally, the interface for FPGA kernels is simplified to reduce differences with other backends, eliminating code rewriting tools to translate Controller kernels into compilable OpenCL code. This simplifies the compilation process and interoperability between backends.

To enable memory optimizations prevented by pointer aliasing, which are critical in FPGA kernels, a new data type was added, the *KHitTileR* (Kernel HitTile Restricted). Although this data type could be used in the kernel parameter declarations of all backends, the performance improvements achieved are only critical in the case of the FPGA backend. Listing 1.3 shows the interface of an FPGA-specific kernel implementation of the stencil shown in listing 1.2.

Listing 1.3. Changes to the generic kernel 2D 4-point stencil 1.2 for FPGA implementation.

```
CTRL_KERNEL_FN(updateCell_4, FPGA, NDRANGE,
    KHitTileR_arg(float, matrix), KHitTileR_arg(float, matrixCopy),
    K_arg(Epsilod_ext, ext_params)) {
    ...
    CTRL_KERNEL_END();
}
```

Due to the compilation particularities of FPGAs, as well as certain OpenCL particularities, this Controller’s backend presents some operational differences to

the others. For performance reasons, FPGA kernels should not be compiled just-in-time like regular OpenCL kernels. Thus, FPGA kernels have to be defined in files separate from the host code and include a different header file. Additionally, generic kernels do not support FPGA compilation.

The original EPSILOG launches the same kernel to compute the borders, and later the inner part of the local data structures, simply changing runtime parameters. For FPGA optimizations it is important to fix the input-size parameters at compile time. This derives in the need to use different compiled kernels for computing the borders on each dimension and the inner part. Consequently, EPSILOG's structure is changed to support different kernel implementations of the same stencil for the borders and the inner part.

5 Experimental study

An experimental evaluation is conducted to assess the performance of EPSILOG, concurrently leveraging CPU, GPU, and FPGA devices in the same execution. The experiments are conducted in *Unicornio*, a highly heterogeneous system of one node comprising:

- An Intel Xeon Silver 4310 CPU, clocked at 2.10GHz, with 12 physical cores and 24 logical threads.
- An NVIDIA TITAN BLACK GPU.
- An Intel Agilex-7 FPGA (DE10-Agilex Development Kit).

This simple system allows us to test the viability of EPSILOG as a stencil framework for highly-heterogeneous systems. EPSILOG is able to adapt to the capabilities of the system, leveraging concurrently all the supported devices.

The operating system is Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS. The host compiler used is GCC version 10.5.0 with $-O3$ levels of optimization. We used the OpenMP library from Intel oneAPI version 2024.1, since it presents lower overheads in nested thread management (a feature leveraged by EPSILOG) than GNU's library. The CUDA version used is 11.6, since it is the last one supporting the Maxwell architecture of the TITAN Black GPU. The FPGA kernel compiler is AOC 21.2.0 Build 67.4. The MPI implementation is MPICH 4.2.3. Device-aware MPI is not used, as there is no device-aware implementation for this combination of devices.

For this evaluation, we use the classical 2D 4-point stencil to solve Poisson's equation with an iterative Jacobi method. See listing 1.1. First, we conduct a study comparing the performance on each device (CPU, GPU, and FPGA) for the same input sizes. We discuss how the results of the first study can be used to calculate the relative weights to balance the load in multi-device scenarios. Then, we conduct a study using all possible combinations of the three devices.

Due to the limited memory capacity of the GPU used (around 6 GiB of RAM), in the first study, the maximum input size tested is $28\,000 \times 28\,000$ elements. For the CPU, 12 execution threads are used (corresponding to the 12 physical cores of the CPU). In all tests, 1000 stencil iterations are executed. The results we present show the average time of 15 executions. We measure the time

Fig. 1. Average execution times for the 2D 4-point stencil for the different implementations and input sizes. Size refers to the length of each dimension of a square matrix.

it takes to compute all iterations of the stencil, disregarding initializations. For CPU and GPU, we use the device-agnostic kernel code in listing 1.2. For FPGA, we test three different implementations:

- A *naïve* implementation, a straightforward translation of the CPU/GPU code to FPGA. See listing 1.3.
- A *parallel* version of the *naïve* implementation, using the same kernel code, but activating automatic vectorization and hardware replication of the kernel via compiler attribute specifiers. The vector size for vectorization is 8 work-items. The kernel is replicated in hardware 4 times. Thus, 32 OpenCL work-items (i.e., computation threads) should be executed at the same time.
- An *optimized* kernel, based on the work of Zohouri *et al.* [20]. It uses a completely different kernel code, designed to leverage shift registers and manual vectorization; but not temporal blocking, as EPSILOG does not yet support it. Comparing it with the original implementation of Zohouri *et al.*, using the same configuration (vector size of 16 elements, no temporal blocking), shows EPSILOG incurs only a 5.27% performance degradation.

5.1 Study 1: Single devices

The results of this experiment can be found in Figure 1. For FPGAs, it can be seen that the performance portability of device-agnostic codes is low. Although the *parallel* FPGA implementation leverages 32 work-items at the same time, it is only 2x faster than the *naïve* one. This is due to data access and management inefficiencies in the implemented hardware. These are solved in the *optimized* version. FPGA performance still remains lower than that of other accelerators, due to the lack of temporal blocking. The last observation is that the execution time is proportional to the input size independently of the device or implementation. Thus, to estimate the relative computing power of two devices for this

application, it is possible to use their difference in execution time for a given input size. For our study, we chose the reference size $28\,000 \times 28\,000$ elements.

5.2 Study 2: Heterogeneous performance of EPSILOG

In this study, we test EPSILOG using several devices at the same time. To study weak scalability in a heterogeneous environment, we want to choose an input size and apply a weighted load partition such that every device takes approximately the same time to compute its assigned load.

In our test system, it is observed that the GPU is the fastest device, but also the one with the smallest memory capacity. To exploit 100% of the computing resources of the whole system, the GPU should handle as much of the computation as it can, with the other devices performing as much work as possible without slowing it down. To achieve this, we use the following formulae to distribute the load proportionally to the devices' speed for this problem. Let T_{gpu} be the execution time of the GPU with the biggest input size supported ($28\,000 \times 28\,000$). We fix the matrix columns to 28 000 elements. Let R_{gpu} be the number of rows in the GPU (28 000) and T_d be the execution time of device d for the reference input size ($28\,000 \times 28\,000$). The total number of rows R is computed for each scenario (set of devices) as follows.

$$R = \sum_d R_{gpu} \times W_d, \text{ with } W_d = \frac{T_{gpu}}{T_d}, d \in \{gpu, cpu, fpga\}$$

We test two different data partition policies. *Regular* is the common homogeneous partition that divides the rows evenly among the devices. *Weighted* is a heterogeneous partition policy that applies the weight W_d to calculate the number of rows assigned to device d . As test scenarios, we consider all possible combinations of a single, two, or three devices being used simultaneously.

The results of these experiments are shown in Figure 2. In the single-device scenarios, both partitions lead to the same situation. Thus, the execution times are the same. The third bar on each scenario represents the number of rows relative to the GPU that leads to a similar execution time. The CPU and FPGA are slower, and their relative input sizes are smaller. In the multi-device scenarios, we observe how the regular partition results in a load imbalance situation, leading to an increase in the execution time. In contrast, the weighted partition policy maintains a similar execution time across all scenarios. This indicates that EPSILOG obtains a good heterogeneous weak scalability, with less than 4% increase in execution time compared to using a single GPU. This allows processing larger input sizes in the same time: Up to 42.43%, when combining all devices.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we expand EPSILOG, a C/C++ high-productivity parallel programming skeleton for iterative stencil computations on distributed heterogeneous systems, to support concurrent execution on FPGAs alongside other kinds

Fig. 2. Heterogeneous scenarios: The scenarios are represented on the x-axis. Two bars represent the execution times with each partition policy (left y-axis), and the third bar represents the number of rows relative to the GPU scenario (right y-axis).

of devices and accelerators. The new EPSILOG version can exploit highly heterogeneous systems comprising multicore CPUs, GPUs, and FPGAs. The solution enables the integration and interoperability of kernels, whether generic or optimized for specific devices. We present an experimental study to show the efficiency of EPSILOG using one classical heat-transfer stencil as a case study, and a single-node system with one CPU, GPU, and FPGA. In the first part of the study, we show the efficiency of EPSILOG for each type of device and discuss the suitability of a simple method to identify the weights that measure the different computational power of the devices. This information is used in the second part of the study to compare the performance of a regular homogeneous partition and a load-balancing weighted partition on all possible combinations of the different devices being used simultaneously. The study shows that EPSILOG can effectively balance the load among computing devices of different kinds, and efficiently leverage all the computational resources in the system. In our basic test system, EPSILOG can compute stencils with a domain 42.43% larger than only using the GPU, in the same amount of time.

Future work includes extending EPSILOG to support temporal blocking to enable further stencil kernel optimizations in FPGAs, developing tools for automatic FPGA-optimized stencil kernel generation, testing automatic load-balancing mechanisms, testing more heterogeneous systems (with multiple GPUs of different vendors), and testing different and more complex stencil operations, such as non-compact, asymmetric, and 3D stencils.

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